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Exploring the Relationship between Translation and Social Behaviour: An Investigation of Bible Translation in Malayalam

Dr. Pratheesh Peter¹

Abstract

Translation plays a crucial role in shaping social behaviour and cultural understanding. The study mainly focuses on understanding the relationship between *Bible* translation into the Malayalam language and its influence on social behavior within the Malayalam-speaking community. It also gives light on the ways in which translation influences language, values, beliefs, and societal interactions. Translation is not just a linguistic process; it also has important social and cultural implications. The translation of the *Bible* into Malayalam has had a profound impact on the social behaviour and culture of the people of Kerala. The Malayalam *Bible* translation has also played a critical role in shaping the social behavior of the people of Kerala. The teachings of the *Bible* have been used to promote social justice and equality. The *Bible* has also been used to promote education and literacy, which has led to the development of a more educated and enlightened society. The followers of Christianity gave more importance to spread education to every section of the society. The Christian community has made a significant contribution to Kerala culture, particularly in the areas of education, society, and culture.

Keywords- Bible, Behaviour, Culture, Christianity, Translation

Translation is an essential process that helps people from different linguistic backgrounds to communicate with each other. “The process of translation can be said to be linguistic,

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intellectual and intuitive at the same time” (Gopinathan, 11). It is a critical tool for the propagation of knowledge, ideas, and culture. The translation of religious texts, including the *Bible*, has played a vital role in disseminating religious beliefs and practices across different cultures and languages. The study will explore the translation of the *Bible* into Malayalam, a language spoken in the southern Indian state of Kerala, and its impact on social behavior.

Malayalam is a language spoken by the people of Kerala, a state situated in the southwestern part of India. Kerala has a rich history of cultural and linguistic diversity, and the Malayalam language has evolved over the years to reflect this diversity. The first Malayalam *Bible* translation was completed in the year 1808. The translation work was carried out by Tamil scholar Thimmappila, Kayamkulam Philipose Ramban, Malpan Pulikottil Joseph and Ittoop Ramban. “Even though the translation was completed in 1808, it was printed and published from Bobay Courier Press in 1811 A.D. This *Bible* is the first printed Bible in Malayalam” (Thampy 67). Since then, several translations of the Bible have been produced in Malayalam, each reflecting the linguistic and cultural nuances of the language.

The Malayalam *Bible* translation has been a critical factor in the spread of Christianity in Kerala. The translation allowed people to read and understand the *Bible* in their native language, which made Christianity more relatable and accessible. This led to a significant increase in the number of people who converted to Christianity in Kerala.

Translation and Social Behavior

Translation is not just a linguistic process; it also has important social and cultural implications. The translation of the *Bible* into Malayalam has had a profound impact on the social behaviour and culture of the people of Kerala since “a culture is a group’s shared values and conventions which act as mental guideline for orienting people’s thoughts and behaviour” (House 12). The social groups across the world follow different social behaviour and values. The translator makes adaptations while rendering so that the target culture can be incorporated or restored while translating a text into target language. This can be seen in the *Bible* translations. For instance, the cultural representations like *Nilaviḷakku*, *Para* etc.,

are used as such in Malayalam Bible translations. The Christian communities in Kerala, begin their prayers by kindling *Nilaviḷakku*. In Kerala the lamp is used during ceremonial events and lighting the *Nilaviḷakku* is regarded as sacred and propitious in native culture. Here one can see the amalgamation of different cultures.

The way a culture is portrayed is important in the translation process as it can affect how the target audience perceives the source culture. On one hand, accurate representation can help readers understand the source culture; while on the other hand, adaptation to their own culture can make the text relatable. However, there may be instances where the translation loses some of the original meaning. Nevertheless, there are also opportunities for a positive exchange of cultural ideas. Likewise, *Para* is also incorporated in Malayalam Bible translations. The *Para* is a container utilized for measuring paddy in Kerala and is often used on auspicious occasions, symbolizing the prosperity of the people. Likewise, the term *śrīkovil* refers to a sacred place within a temple, and translators use this word to convey the sanctity of the location. By incorporating these cultural words and symbols into their translations, Bible translators were able to introduce the cultural significance of these items to Kerala's native society, recognizing and valuing their rich traditions.

Christianity, as a religion, emphasizes love, kindness, respect and compassion. These teachings or values can be seen or reflected in the teachings of the Bible, and the translation of the Bible into Malayalam has helped to disseminate these values throughout Kerala. The Bible has been used to teach people about the importance of treating others with respect and kindness, and this has contributed to the development of a more compassionate and empathetic society.

The Malayalam Bible translation has also played a critical role in shaping the social behaviour of the people of Kerala. The teachings of the Bible have been used to promote social justice and equality. For example, the Bible teaches that all people are equal in the eyes of God, and this has been used to promote equality and social justice in Kerala. The Bible has also been used to promote education and literacy, which has led to the development of a more educated and enlightened society. The followers of Christianity gave more importance to spread education to every section of the society. The Christian community has made a significant contribution to Kerala

culture, particularly in the areas of education, society, and culture. The main goal of Indian Christian churches is to eradicate the social ills caused by caste-based divisions. Indian culture was governed by the caste system, and untouchability was a widespread occurrence. Indian churches' main goal is to end these sinful customs. It was believed that the only way to eradicate such ill practices from society was through education. Therefore, schools and colleges were created by Christian churches across Kerala. They propagated the motto of Education to all as part of its evangelization and as a result, the stories and parables from the *Bible* had to be translated into Malayalam. There were released a number of books for different educational levels. They gained enormous popularity among neo literates.

Chavara Kuriakose Elias, one of the renowned social reformers of Kerala issued a decree which says that there should have a school attached to every parish church which helped to make free education available for every one irrespective of caste, creed and community. Schools or *vidyālayam*, thus got the pseudonym *paḷḷikkūṭam*, and the expression *paḷḷiyuṃ paḷḷikkūṭavuṃ* became very popular.

The use of culturally significant terms and word coinages like *suviṣeṣam*, *vidyālayam*, *śrikovil* in Bible translation has a linguistic and cultural impact that serves as a link between the two language communities. As a result, the native society is able to overcome its "fear of the unknown" and accept these kinds of translations as well as similar Christian culture. *The New Testament* gives the guidelines and the way as to how the Christians should live and follow values or ethics like love and compassion towards the under privileged people in their lives, and how they should cultivate and establish humility and gentleness in society, and how to foster communal harmony, Christians frequently incorporate native symbols into their religious practises. Therefore, according to the *Bible*, morality and ethics are concerned with the welfare of society rather than just one person's character. "Christian ethics is with the whole of human welfare: it is both 'this worldly and other worldly'. It considers body and soul as factors in the good life: the physical world of nature and the spiritual as parts of the divine scheme. There is nothing novel in such statements: with varying emphases most Christians are living in accordance with them" (D'Souza 227).

The Malayalam *Bible* translation has also contributed to the

development of a more pluralistic society in Kerala. Christianity, as a religion, highlighted the importance of tolerance and acceptance of others. The translation of the *Bible* into Malayalam has helped to promote these values in Kerala. The *Bible* has been used to teach people about the importance of respecting other religions and cultures, and this has contributed to the development of a more diverse and pluralistic society in Kerala.

Malayalam literary works bear witness to the influence and impact of the Bible translations upon the target culture and its literature. Some examples are given below;

Ezham Mudra by Kaakkanadan.

Ayussinte Pusthakam by C.V. Balakrishnan.

Avan Veendum Varunnu and

AA Manushyan Ni Thanne by C.J. Thomas.

The Malayalam Bible translation has also had an impact on the language itself. The translation of the Bible into Malayalam has helped to standardize the language and has contributed to its development as a literary language. The translators of the Bible had to grapple with the challenge of rendering the text into a language that was not yet fully developed. As a result, they had to create new words and phrases, which contributed to the growth and development of the language. The influence of these Biblical expressions has spread to the social and political aspects of Kerala, and they have been utilized effectively in journalism, film, and literature, contributing to the diverse range of spoken Malayalam. Prior to the 19th century, the history of Bible translations in Malayalam was almost non-existent, and the language's prose was in an unstable state. However, during the 19th and 20th centuries, Malayalam prose underwent an unprecedented level of progress in various fields.

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